

**PARTICIPATION OF CITIZENS IN THE PROCESS OF NORM- MAKING
IN ESTABLISHING CIVIL SOCIETY: SOME THEORETICAL-LEGAL
ISSUES**

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Abstract. This article analyzes the participation of citizens in the process of norm creation in the establishment of a civil society, and its specific features. Based on the discussion of the existing problems, scientifically based proposals are put forward. The article can be used in scientific research on the participation of citizens in the process of creating norms.

Keywords: norm-making, citizen participation, civil society, law, normative-legal act.

Human society has experienced many management forms and methods in its historical development. Humanity has always strived for a higher level. As a result of these aspirations, today, modern democratic states have already begun to take practical steps towards the establishment of a civil society.

Civil society is valuable in that it expresses many positive aspects, such as the high level of human rights and freedoms, the guarantee of private property, the legal organization of state power and the principle of separation of powers, and the establishment of the rule of law in society. After all, the leader of our country paid attention to the urgency of the issue and expressed the following thoughts: "through the development of a free civil society, our large-scale reforms aimed at establishing a people-friendly state, ensuring human dignity and his legitimate interests will rise to a new level."

Undoubtedly, a specific ground must be prepared for the formation of civil society. In particular, it is possible to enumerate cases such as the organization of power on a legal basis and democratic methods and based on the principle of the distribution of powers, the operation of the economy based on the laws of market relations, the diversity of forms of property, the equality of all people before the law, and the guarantee of freedom of speech. Along with the above, the main condition of civil society is the activity of citizens. That is, it can be said that the interest of citizens in society and state affairs, the formation of feelings of involvement in the society in relation to issues directly related to their rights and freedoms, as well as legal interests, and the increase of persons with a strong civil position are of decisive importance. It can be seen that citizens' activism is increasing as a result of legal democratic reforms, especially that they are expressing certain attitudes based on their independent opinions on the adopted laws and regulations. Sufficient conditions must be provided to support this activity.

When talking about the work done in our country in this regard, it should be noted that the adoption of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the Openness of the Activities of State Power and Management Bodies" was a huge step in bringing the state bodies and citizens closer together. According to the law, information on the activities of state power and management bodies includes normative and legal documents adopted by state power and management bodies, normative and other documents, as well as normative and legal documents adopted by state power and management bodies on the progress of their implementation. and the introduction of changes and additions to other documents, as well as the declaration of invalidity of these documents, the introduction of information about the drafts of normative and legal documents, normative and other documents being developed by state authorities and management bodies, was a very big event. And it is very important to create the opportunity to get acquainted with this information for all citizens. Notably, citizens had the opportunity to familiarize themselves with the normative legal documents adopted by the state authorities and management

bodies, as well as the drafts of normative and other documents that are expected to be adopted[1].

Of course, this step forward did not leave its positive echo. The responsibility of the representatives of the state authorities and management bodies has increased, and the citizens' activity has increased.

This year, as a logical continuation of these reforms, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On additional measures to ensure the openness of the activities of state bodies and organizations, as well as effective implementation of public control" was adopted. Among the many changes stipulated in the decree, it should be noted that from December 1, 2021, the sessions of the Legislative Chamber and Senate of the Oliy Majlis, the Dzhokorgi Council of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, the sessions of the Regional, District, and City Council of People's Deputies will be broadcasted live through TV channels and the Internet[2].

In many areas of the state power and administration, the open and transparent process of rule-making and the active participation of citizens in it will not only improve the quality of the adopted laws and regulations, but also lead to the establishment of close cooperation between state bodies and citizens[3].

There is another side to the matter, which is not only an active citizenship position requires openness and responsibility from the state authorities and management bodies, as well as necessary knowledge and skills, high legal awareness and legal culture from citizens. In particular, the role of legal consciousness and legal culture is important in the direct participation of citizens in the process of developing normative legal documents, the expression of high-quality and useful suggestions and comments, and in general, the effective participation in the activity of creating norms[4]. With a deep understanding of this law, all layers of the population can achieve legal literacy, in order to create a comprehensive systematic system of educating citizens who are strong-willed, who know their rights and respect the law, who can apply their legal knowledge in everyday life, who have an active civil

position and who have an intolerant attitude towards crime. On January 9, 2019, the Concept of Improving Legal Culture in Society was approved. In the concept, tasks such as broadcasting of analytical talk shows, debate-oriented shows and broadcasts reflecting the opinion and attitude of independent experts, specialists and residents were defined in the adopted legislation[5].

Participation of citizens in the process of norm creation will encourage civil society to take further steps forward. In particular, in the "Concept of development of civil society in 2021-2025" the task of improving the legal basis of the participation of non-governmental non-profit organizations at all stages of the development of draft laws, including the process of submission to the Cabinet of Ministers, was defined[6]. This means that citizens and their associations who want to participate in the process of developing, changing or canceling the currently adopted legal norms are invited to cooperate.

It is becoming increasingly clear that citizen activism can be of great help to the state today. Citizens united in various social projects have the opportunity to discuss emerging, emerging and existing problems, find their solutions and propose them to the government.

Based on the above, in order to further accelerate the work aimed at ensuring the more active participation of citizens in the process of norm creation, which is one of the important conditions for the development of civil society, the following It is appropriate to pay attention to.

Taking measures to systematically increase their imagination and knowledge about the process of development, discussion and adoption of draft normative legal documents while increasing the legal consciousness and legal culture of citizens. Including citizens as subjects of social partnership in the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Social Partnership". After all, social partnership is the development and implementation of social and economic development programs of the country, including network and regional programs, as well as normative legal documents and other decisions related to the rights and legal interests of citizens, with non-

governmental non-profit organizations and other institutions of civil society cooperation.

Based on the fact that the portal for the discussion of draft regulatory legal documents is a platform that has a positive effect on the quality of adopted regulatory legal documents and directly connects citizens with competent state bodies, it is necessary to further expand the capabilities of the platform. In particular, it is advisable to introduce functions not only to make suggestions on the projects discussed on the platform, but also to vote in support of the project or suggestions made to it. It is necessary to establish special television programs, debates and discussions that allow to attract the general public on the results of the discussion, not limited to online monitoring of the discussion of regulatory legal documents conducted by the competent state bodies.

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